

Local Government in Austria

Responses to Urban-Rural Challenges

edited by

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The H2020-MSCA-RISE-2018 project aims to provide solutions for local governments that address the fundamental challenges resulting from urbanisation. To address these complex issues, 18 partners from 17 countries and six continents share their expertise and knowledge in the realms of public law, political science, and public administration. LoGov identifies, evaluates, compares, and shares innovative practices that cope with the impact of changing urban-rural relations in major local government areas (WP 1-5).

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Local Responsibilities and Public Services

2.1. Local Responsibilities and Public Services in Austria: An Introduction

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Local governments in Austria perform their own autonomous functions (*eigener Wirkungsbereich*)⁶ as well as tasks delegated by the federation and the respective *Land* (*übertragener Wirkungsbereich*). According to Article 116 of the Federal Constitution all municipalities have the same rights and duties (principle of the *Einheitsgemeinde*) except for the so-called 'statutory cities' (*Statutarstädte*), and Vienna which is both a municipality and a *Land*.⁷

Local authorities, both urban (ULGs) and rural (RLGs) municipalities, are responsible for a wide range of public services, including the provision of infrastructure, kindergartens, primary schools, retirement homes, etc. As stated by the Federal Constitution they are independent economic entities (Article 116(2) of the Federal Constitution⁸), and as such can contribute to the general economy with running their own industrial and commercial enterprises.

However, depending on the type of service, Austrian municipalities provide public services in different ways. The provision of public services ranges from self-operated municipal companies to public-private partnerships.⁹

⁶ Own responsibility tasks are local police, markets, traffic facilities, land use planning, social services, water, sanitation and waste, sports and leisure time facilities. In spite of their self-governing status, the municipalities in these respects have to obey *Länder* and federal laws and are subject to control in legal and efficiency terms. The *Länder* oversee the budgets of municipalities with reference to economy, profitability, and expediency. The standards of supervision vary considerably between the *Länder*.

⁷ See the Introduction to the System of Local Government in Austria, report section 1.

⁸ All municipalities are corporations and have the right to own property, run businesses, levy municipal taxes, and generally manage their own financial affairs: '*Die Gemeinde ist selbständiger Wirtschaftskörper. Sie hat das Recht, innerhalb der Schranken der allgemeinen Bundes- und Landesgesetze Vermögen aller Art zu besitzen, zu erwerben und darüber zu verfügen, wirtschaftliche Unternehmungen zu betreiben sowie im Rahmen der Finanzverfassung ihren Haushalt selbständig zu führen und Abgaben auszusprechen.*'

⁹ The instruments of public service delivery include: Communal self-supply through enterprises owned and operated by the municipality itself. The *Stadtwerke* as an organizational part of the municipal administration formed the economic foundation of municipal autonomy. Communal enterprises as independent companies organized under private law. These 'out-sourced' communal enterprises do not only deliver public utilities' services but also increasingly operate cultural or social infrastructures. Communal ordering of services by commissioning private companies. In recent years the ordering of services has got a decisive boost and has replaced the communal enterprise as a means of providing public services in some areas.

Public procurement has become a central instrument for securing public utilities. With the Public service concession, the municipality transfers the right for full or partial provision of public services to a third party. Public Private Partnerships which are used in particular for areas of public utilities that require high infrastructure costs (e.g. hospitals, school campuses, etc.).

Particularly in the last two decades, the municipalities in Austria have increasingly become service providers for citizens rather than being mere administrative authorities. As there is no difference regarding the size or population of municipalities in the Federal Constitutional Law, fulfilling all these local responsibilities can be challenging especially for small Austrian municipalities. Thus, inter-municipal cooperation is a key feature of local government in Austria to provide the necessary economies of scale and expertise that individual municipalities are lacking.¹⁰ Hence, municipal associations (*Gemeindeverbände*, Article 116(a)) play a crucial role in public service delivery managing, for example water supply or waste management.

Similar to most of the Western European countries ULGs and RLGs in Austria need to tackle different challenges in delivering public services. However, the decrease in public resources together with an increase of public tasks are the main challenges that all Austrian municipalities are facing, due to demographic changes (ageing, migration from rural areas to urban areas), climate change, societal changes (Generation Y, migration and segregation), land take and scarcity, energy transformation and digitization.

Impact of Demographic Changes on the Provision of Local Public Services

Rural migration and the influx of population into urban areas puts the provision of public services as the central cornerstones of good living conditions under more and more pressure and increases the urban-rural divide. Austria's population is growing, but there are significant regional differences and many rural regions are affected by population declines. It is the cities and their surrounding regions that are driving population growth in Austria. The population forecast of the Austrian Conference on Spatial Planning (ÖROK) from 2018¹¹ assumes that the population of Austria will grow by further 710,000 people (+ 8.0 per cent) by 2040. The nine largest cities in Austria – Vienna, Graz, Linz, Salzburg, Innsbruck, Klagenfurt, Villach, Wels and St. Pölten – will account for almost two thirds of the country's forecast population growth in 2040.

In the past ten years, four out of ten Austrian municipalities have shrunk. The decline affects mainly RLGs in Upper Styria, Upper Carinthia and the northern *Waldviertel* and *Weinviertel* in Lower Austria. Most of these RLGs are located far away from economic centers and have poor transport connections.

On the one hand economically weak RLGs but also structurally weak ULGs are increasingly losing younger and well-educated people. At the same time, the proportion of elderly people is rising. The population forecast of the Austrian Conference on Spatial Planning (ÖROK) from

¹⁰ For detailed information on inter-municipal cooperation, see report section 4 on local government structure.

¹¹ Österreichische Raumordnungskonferenz ÖROK, 'Kleinräumige Bevölkerungsprognose für Österreich 2018 bis 2040 mit einer Projektion bis 2060 und Modellfortschreibung bis 2075 (ÖROK-Prognose)' (ÖROK 2019) <https://www.oerok.gv.at/fileadmin/user_upload/Bilder/2.Reiter-Raum_u._Region/2.Daten_und_Grundlagen/Bevoelkerungsprognosen/Prognose_2018/Bericht_BevPrognose_2018.pdf> accessed 7 November 2019.

2018 believes that in some rural peripheral areas by 2040 more than a third of the population could be over 65 years old. Migration not only changes social life, it also has a negative impact on vacancy and real estate prices, making it more and more difficult to provide services of general interest close to home, and worsens employment and income prospects.

Figure 1: Statistik Austria (POPREG, ÖROK-Prognosis 2018).¹²

On the other hand, economically strong ULGs – especially the capital cities of the Austrian *Länder*– have benefited from immigration both from other Austrian regions and from abroad and are continuously growing (see figure above). But growth also means a shortage of housing, and public infrastructure is continuously reaching the limits of its capacity and resilience. The boost of commuters together with an unfavorable modal split and the coexistence of people with different ethnic and cultural backgrounds pose further challenges on growing ULGs in Austria.

In order to meet these challenges in both RLGs and ULGs, the promotion of cooperation between municipalities to provide public services in Austria has become a priority on the political agenda. Nonetheless, the approaches for RLGs and ULGs differ. Recognizing the importance of functional areas, ULGs are increasingly trying to develop integrated strategies and projects for territorial cooperation together with their often rural neighboring municipalities. This latest development was driven by the current Austrian spatial development

¹² Graph: Ramon Bauer and Tina Frank, 'Österreichs Städte in Zahlen 2020' (Österreichischer Städtebund 2020).

concept (ÖREK 2011) and the partnership ‘Cooperation Platform Urban Regions’, which was mainly supported by the Austrian Association of Cities.¹³

With regards to RLGs, the so-called *Master Plan ländlicher Raum* in 2017¹⁴ gave a boost to rethinking municipal cooperation as a vital instrument, not only for the better delivering of public services, but also for safeguarding Austria’s rural areas. The *Masterplan ländlicher Raum* is the result of a broad participation process from autumn 2016 until summer 2017 aimed at sounding out possible solutions for strengthening the rural areas, which was initiated by the then Minister of Agriculture.

Regrettably, the *Masterplan ländlicher Raum* mainly targets RLGs, and lacks a holistic approach to spatial development. Although the *Masterplan ländlicher Raum* promotes inter-municipal cooperation as an important implementation tool for the provision of public services, it is not seen as a strategic instrument for integrated territorial development. Paying too less attention to functional areas where ULGs are essential partners for RLGs in delivering public services like public transport hinders a successful urban-rural interplay and contributes to the urban-rural divide.

With the current project of the Austrian Conference on Spatial Planning (ÖROK) on strengthening regional governance including both ULGs and RLGs a first important step towards fostering urban-rural linkages has been set.

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¹³ See the Introduction to the Structure of Local Government in Austria, report section 4.1.

¹⁴ Bundesministerium für Land- und Forstwirtschaft, Nachhaltigkeit und Wasserwirtschaft, ‘Masterplan ländlicher Raum’ (BMLFUW 2017) <<https://www.bmlrt.gv.at/service/publikationen/land/masterplan-laendlicher-raum.html>> accessed 6 November 2019.

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